

A Study of Some Properties of Nitrocellulose made from Jute with Special Reference to its Stability.

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In view of the large output and economic importance of jute fibre, it would be interesting to investigate if this fibre could at least partly replace cotton or linter as a source of cellulose. In the following work some of the properties, particularly the stability, of jute nitrocellulose (*Corchorus capsularis*) have been studied and compared with those of cotton (*Gossypium herbaceum*).*

Nitrocellulose as prepared from jute fibre has been studied by Cross and Bevan (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1880, 38, 667; 1889, 55, 202) and by Mühlhäuser (*Dingl. Polyt. J.*, 1882, 284, 137). The former obtained an unstable product though it is not known whether they attempted to improve the stability while Mühlhäuser did not investigate the stability of his product. Owing to the technical importance of stability of nitrocelluloses, attempts have been made in these investigations to obtain a product from jute as stable as that from cotton and to get an idea of the ingredients which cause instability of jute nitrocellulose. It is satisfactory to note that nitrocellulose from jute has been made as stable as that from cotton though the fibrous structure was lost to a considerable degree during the process of stabilisation and the solution in ether-alcohol was found considerably less viscous than the corresponding solution of nitrated cotton. This is however an advantage for certain purposes, *e.g.*, for lacquer industry where low viscosity solutions are preferred.

In the course of stabilising the nitrocellulose, it has been found that continued boiling, particularly with acidulated water, degraded the product. Moderate acid-boiling must be followed by thorough washing with dilute alkali and water. The best stability results were however obtained by boiling with alcohol which dissolved the unstable sugar nitrates. Even the untreated raw fibre may thus be made to yield a very stable light-brown product, nitro-lignin being evidently dissolved by alcohol.

* Jute used in these experiments belonged to the variety known as *Bengal Kortha* and was obtained locally. Cotton used in these experiments was of 'Sarat' type obtained through the courtesy of Dhakeswari Cotton Mills Ltd.

The different stability tests did not give identical results. The low temperature Abel test was found quite useful in detecting highly unstable products but was of little value when comparatively stable sugar-nitrates were present. For this purpose however the German 135° test was quite satisfactory, as most sugar-nitrates decomposed near about this temperature (Will and Lenze, *Ber.*, 1898, 31, 68).

Nitration of Cotton and Jute.

Previous treatment.—For the purpose of nitration, cotton was purified by boiling with 1% caustic soda solution for one hour and the moisture content kept constant (0.5—1%). Jute was nitrated in different stages of purification. Whenever delignified fibre was used, it was prepared by chlorine peroxide method as cellulose and the accompanying carbohydrates are least affected by this reagent.

Procedure.—10 G. samples of purified and dried cellulose were nitrated in a large beaker by immersion in 500 g. acid mixture, the proportion of sulphuric acid, nitric acid and water being respectively as 61.2:21.2:17.6. This mixture was constantly stirred and nitration continued for 45 minutes during which time the maximum temperature attained was 32—35°, while the initial temperature of the bath ranged from 22 to 25°. The bulk of the acid was then removed by pressing the product on a perforated disc and the nitro-cellulose suddenly immersed in a large volume of cold distilled water. Washing with cold water was then continued until the wash-water was neutral to litmus.

The following table shows some of the results obtained with jute and cotton nitrocelluloses. In the case of jute, the delignified fibre was purified to some extent by treatment with 5% caustic soda solution in the cold so that the cellulose and hemicelluloses would not be materially affected while the acid constituents would be largely removed.

TABLE I.

Properties and yield of nitrocelluloses from cotton and jute.

Cellulose.	Yield.	Solubility in ether-alcohol.	Rate of flow.	Nitrogen content.
Cotton ...	157%	98%	4 secs.	12%
Jute ...	139	95	0.5	12.05

It will be noted from the above table that the yield of nitro-cellulose from jute is much smaller. This is partly due to mechanical loss during the process of washing when the nitrated fibre

crumbles to powder but mainly to the presence of considerable amount of γ -cellulose which give water-soluble nitro-compounds.

A mixture of ether and alcohol (55:45) has been used as solvent for determining solubility while viscosity has been determined at 20° in 1% ether-alcoholic solution. For this purpose the falling sphere viscometer of Gibson and Jacobs has been used, the sphere having a diameter of 1/16 inch and the column of solution having 1 cm. diameter and 20 cm. length. The considerably low viscosity in the case of jute may be due to either physical or chemical differences in the cellulose constituent of the fibres, as similar results have been obtained also with carefully purified jute cellulose. It is probable that the degree of polymerisation of jute cellulose is less or that its micells are shorter than those of cotton. The stability results (Table VI) are not apparently influenced by this difference. As has already been observed, this low viscosity is not without its technical advantage for certain purposes.

Attention may also be drawn to the lower solubility of jute nitrocellulose though its viscosity is lower and the nitrogen content identical. It is evident that owing to the presence of foreign matters, the product obtained from jute is less homogeneous than that from cotton, the percentage of nonnitrated or lower nitrated cellulose being greater.

That the nitration of jute is retarded by non-celluloses is evident from the nitrogen content of different nitrocelluloses obtained by nitrating jute fibre of different degrees of purity. This is brought out by the following table.

TABLE II.

Effect of impurities on nitration of cellulose.

Fibre.	Method of purification.	Nitrogen content.
Cotton	Boiled with 1% caustic soda.	12.0%
Jute	Treated thrice with 18% (cold) and once with 5% (hot) alkali.	12.1
"	Treated once with 18% alkali.	11.85
"	Delignified and treated several times with 5% cold alkali.	12.05
"	Delignified and extracted with water and alcohol under pressure.	12.0
"	Delignified and extracted with water and alcohol at atmospheric pressure.	11.9
"	Delignified only.	11.9
"	Boiled once with 0.5% alkali.	10.8

Stabilisation of Nitrocellulose.

After removal of any adhering acids by repeated washing with cold water, the samples of nitrated cellulose were given four sour boils with 1% hydrochloric acid, each of four hours' duration, followed by neutral boilings with distilled water, two or three alkali-boilings with 0.3% sodium carbonate and finally by repeated washing with boiling water. The scheme of washing and the corresponding stability figures by both the 76° Abel test and the 185° German test are shown in the following table.

TABLE III.

Stabilisation of nitrated α -cellulose from jute.

Nitrogen content = 11.85%. Period of boiling = 4 hours each.

No. of acid boilings.	No. of alkali boilings.	No. of water boilings.	Abel test.	Stability (in mins.)		
				Appearance of colour.	German test.	
					Complete colour.	Brown fumes.
4	—	—	6	3	—	—
4	—	8	12	15	25	35
4	2	6	12	20	30	45

It will be apparent from the above table that boiling with dilute alkali after preliminary acid boiling is favourable and gives better stability figures by the 185° German test, the number and period of boiling being the same. Sulphuric acid could not be detected in the wash after the first two acid boilings. Prolonged heating with acid had a deleterious effect, due probably to the formation of fresh unstable products. Boiling with 1% hydrochloric acid alone even up to 100 hours could not render nitrocellulose at all stable. It was also found that the stability increased gradually on heating the sour-boiled nitrocellulose with water for increased periods of time. This was found useful in comparing stability of nitrocelluloses of different degrees of purity.

TABLE IVa.

Stabilisation of nitrocellulose from jute treated with 5% alkali.

Nitrogen content = 12.05%. Period of boiling = 4 hours each.

No. of acid boilings.	No. of water boilings.	Stability (in mins.)	German test.		
			Abel test.	Appearance of colour.	Complete colour.
4	8	12	5	10	—
4	6	15	15	20	35
4	9	—	20	25	35
4	12	—	25	35	45
4	14	—	25	35	60

TABLE IVb.

Stabilisation of cotton nitrocellulose.

Nitrogen content = 12.0%. Period of boiling = 4 hours each.

No. of acid boilings.	No. of water boilings.	Stability (in mins.)	German test.		
			Abel test.	Appearance of colour.	Complete colour.
4	8	15	3	5	—
4	6	30	10	15	15
4	9	—	20	25	30
4	12	—	25	30	40
4	14	—	25	30	50

The above tables bring out the fact that increase of stability is of the same order in the case of both cotton and jute cellulose-nitrates. The slightly higher result in the case of jute may be due to the fact that nitrated jute was transformed into very fine pulp during the process of washing and as a result, impurities were better removed in this case.

Relative Stability of Nitrocelluloses from Jute of different Degrees of Purity.

Before nitration, the original jute fibre was subjected to different chemical treatments for the removal of different types of impurities such as (1) fats, waxes and resins, (2) lignin, (3) hemicelluloses and (4) pectin matters. The following tables give the stability results of the different nitrated jute cellulose.

(a) Nitrocellulose from lignified fibre.

Raw jute from which woody tissues were removed mechanically, was cut into small pieces and boiled for one hour with 0.5% caustic soda to remove the greater parts of oils and allied impurities. The following are the analytical data of the fibre.

Moisture	...	1.0%	Lignin	...	12.2%
Ash	0.5%	Furfural	...	9.5%
Fats, etc.	...	traces.			

The nitrocellulose obtained from the above lignified fibre was coloured deep yellow even after repeated washing and its nitrogen content and yield were lower than those of the nitrates obtained from more purified jute cellulose.

TABLE V_a.

Stabilisation of nitrocellulose from raw jute.

Nitrogen content = 10.8%. Period of acid boiling = 4 hrs. each.

Period of alkali and water boiling = 3 hrs. each.

Stability (in mins.)				German test.		
No. of acid boilings.	No. of alkali boilings.	No. of water boilings.	Abel test.	Appearance of colour.	Complete colour.	Brown fumes.
4	—	—	6	—	—	—
4	—	8	25	20	35	60
4	2	6	25	20	40	75

In the above tests, copious fumes were not evolved even after 100 minutes, the figures stated above being only the approximate time when evolution of fumes was suspected. During alkali treatment, the colour of the product changed from yellow to brown and the fibres crumbled to powder though there was no appreciable change in nitrogen content.

(b) *Nitrocellulose from delignified fibre.*

Raw jute, after preliminary treatment with 0.5% caustic soda, was delignified by treatment with chlorine peroxide gas. The following are the analytical data.

Moisture	0.8%	Lignin	nil.
Ash	0.2%	Furfural	7.6%

TABLE Vb.

Stabilisation of nitrocellulose from delignified fibre.

Nitrogen content = 11.3%. Period of washing = 4 hours each.

No. of acid boilings.	No. of water boilings.	Stability (in mins.)			
		Abel test.	Garman test.		
			Appearance of colour.	Complete colour.	Brown fumes.
4	8	27	10	12	15

(c) *Nitrocellulose from delignified fibre extracted with water and alcohol.*

Delignified jute was treated with boiling water for five hours and then with alcohol under reflux for the same period, washed and dried before use. The analytical data are as follows.

Moisture	1.0%	Lignin	nil.
Furfural	6.5%	Uronic carbon dioxide	appreciable.

TABLE Vc.

Stabilisation of nitrocellulose from delignified and extracted fibre.

Nitrogen content = 11.9%. Period of boiling = 4 hrs. each.

No. of acid boilings.	No. of water boilings.	Stability (in mins.)			
		Abel test.	Garman test.		
			Appearance of colour.	Complete colour.	Brown fumes.
4	7	15	5	—	—

(d) *Nitrocellulose from delignified fibre freed further from uronic acids.*

Delignified jute was extracted with water under ordinary pressure and then with alcohol at 3 atmospheres pressure for two hours. It gave Furfural, 5.1 per cent. and Uronic carbon dioxide, nil.

TABLE Vd.

Stabilisation of nitrocellulose from delignified jute, extracted and freed from pectin.

Nitrogen content=12%. Period of each washing=4 hours.

No. of acid boilings.	No. of water boilings.	Stability (in mins.) Abel test.	German test.		
			Appearance of colour.	Complete colour.	Brown fumes.
4	7	18	8	—	—
4	18	—	15	20	40

(e) *Nitrocellulose from delignified jute treated with 5% alkali in the cold.*

The delignified fibre was treated several times in the cold with twenty times its weight of 5% caustic soda, washed with water and dilute acetic acid. Its furfural content was 2.2% and the nitrogen content of the nitrated product was found to be 12.05%. The stability tests are shown in Table IVa.

(f) *Nitrated α -cellulose of jute fibre.*

α -Cellulose was prepared from jute in the usual manner by treatment with 18% alkali, the furfural content being 2.5%. Nitrogen content of the nitrated product was 11.85%. The stability results are shown in Table II.

(g) *Nitrocellulose from purified α -cellulose of jute.*

The α -cellulose, as prepared above from jute, was further treated with 5% boiling caustic soda for one hour. This treatment brought down the furfural content to the lowest figure of 1.1%.

TABLE V_a.

Stabilisation of nitrocellulose from purified α-cellulose.

Nitrogen content=12·1%. Period of each boiling=4 hours.

No. of acid boilings.	No. of water boilings.	Abel test.	German test.		
			Stability (in mins.)	Appearance of colour.	Complete colour.
4	8	12	15	20	80

In the following table, the results of the previous tables are placed together in order to get an idea of the variation of stability with the nature of impurity in the cellulose.

TABLE VI.

Effect of impurities on stability.

Cellulose.	Nitrogen content.	No. of acid boilings.	No. of water boilings.	Stability. Abel test.	German test.			
					App. of colour.	Complete colour.	Brown fumes.	
1. Raw jute	...	10·8%	4	8	25	20	35	80
2. Delignified jute		11·8%	4	8	27	10	12	15
3. " extracted with water and alcohol		11·9%	4	7	15	5	—	—
4. " extracted further with alcohol under pressure		12·0%	4	7	18	3	—	—
5. Jute treated several times with 5% cold alkali		12·05%	4	9	—	20	25	
6. Jute treated once with 18% cold alkali		11·85%	4	8	12	15	25	
7. " boiled further with 5% alkali		12·1%	4	8	12	15	20	80
8. Cotton boiled with 1% alkali.		12·0%	4	9	—	20	25	80

The conclusions from the above results are rather striking. The very high stability in the case of raw jute is due probably to lower nitration while delignified jute gives a less stable product with a higher nitrogen content. It is therefore evident that lignin does

not affect stability. With higher nitrogen content (samples 3 and 4), the stability of nitrocellulose is found to decrease to some extent, and attains a satisfactory figure only after prolonged boiling. Thus thirteen boilings were necessary to stabilise sample 4 (Table Vc.) in a satisfactory manner. Attention may also be drawn to samples 3—8, where the nitrogen contents are practically the same but stability results are widely different. It is probable that in samples 3—4, alkali-soluble carbohydrates are present which on nitration give unstable sugar-nitrates requiring prolonged boiling for complete removal. When the alkali-soluble impurities are largely removed as in sample 5, the same extent of boiling (9) gives a fairly good result, a more satisfactory value being obtained when the number of boiling is increased to 14 (Table IVa). On further removing these impurities with 18% alkali (sample 6), the stability is found to decrease. This is more prominent in sample 7, which has been subjected to several treatments with concentrated alkali. High concentration of alkali evidently affects the stability of nitrocellulose due to the partial degradation of cellulose itself or to the formation of oxycellulose. The adverse effect of mercerisation on the stability of cotton nitrocellulose has long been reported (Marshall, "Explosives", p. 139). It is stated that 17 hot washings in the case of mercerised cotton did not give the same stability figure as seven washes in the case of standard cotton.

In practice, therefore, it is more advisable to treat delignified cellulose with cold alkali of moderate strength. It will be observed that the stability of nitrocellulose from jute treated with 5% cold alkali is almost identical by the German test, though the Abel test always gives a slightly higher result in the case of cotton nitrocellulose.

Stabilisation by Washing with Alcohol.

Since alcohol is invariably used in all nitrocellulose industries either as a solvent or as dehydrating and gelatinising agents, it was thought advisable to study the method of stabilisation with alcohol. It has been found that in all cases very high stability is attained by treatment with alcohol, provided the greater portion of combined sulphuric acid is previously removed by means of preliminary acid boiling. A large number of experiments were made; only the more important and typical results are shown in the following table.

TABLE VII.

Stabilisation of nitrocellulose by treatment with alcohol.

Nitrocellulose from—	No. of acid boilings (4 hrs. each).	Period of alcohol treatment (days).	Stability German test.	
			Coloration.	Fumes.
Cotton	4	—	5	15
"	4	3	20	45
"	—	3	10	15
Jute	2	—	5	10
"	2	3	15	25
"	4	—	5	15
"	4	3	25	60
Cotton	2	—	10	15
"	2	3	20	35
"	4	3	35	75
Raw jute	4	—	5	10
"	4	10 hrs. (extracted under reflux.)	40	75

It may be noted that highly coloured samples of nitrocellulose are left practically colourless by repeated hot extraction with alcohol. Since it is well-known that bleaching deteriorates all kinds of cellulose forming oxycellulose or causing decomposition, alcohol may be used for bleaching as well as for stabilising nitrated cellulose. The alcohol-soluble impurities however do not usually amount to more than 2% of the weight of nitrocellulose, being slightly greater in the case of jute than of cotton. The nitrogen content of alcohol-extracted nitrocellulose remained the same as before extraction and apart from the removal of undesirable impurities, no loss of nitrocellulose occurred. The nature of the alcohol extract is now under investigation.

Conclusions.

(1) By suitable methods of stabilisation, satisfactory stability may be obtained from jute nitrocellulose, whatever the nature of impurities, usually accompanying the fibre may be.

(2) The greater the impurities in jute cellulose, the more thorough must be the stabilisation of the nitrocellulose.

(3) Washing with acidulated water alone is not sufficient to stabilise jute nitrocellulose but should always be followed by alkaline or neutral washing.

(4) Alcohol has been found to be an excellent stabilising agent.

(5) Very small amounts of sugars or easily hydrolysable pentosans and hexosans (wood gum and hemicelluloses) will cause considerable instability.

(6) Cellulose degraded by the action of concentrated alkali will give unstable products.

(7) The more the impurities in the cellulose, the less will be the nitrogen content of the nitrocellulose made from it.

(8) Uniform nitration of jute is more difficult than that of cotton, unless impurities are carefully removed previously.

(9) Jute nitrocellulose is considerably less viscous than cotton in ether-alcoholic solution, which may be taken to indicate that the two celluloses are not quite identical.

The author wishes to express his indebtedness to Dr. J. K. Chaudhury for suggesting and guiding this work and to Prof. J. C. Ghosh for taking keen interest and affording facilities for carrying it out.

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Received April 30, 1930.